

EXAMINATION OF THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR IN THE MOUNTAINOUS REGION OF ROMANIA: A THOROUGH ANALYSIS SPANNING 2008 TO 2018

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Abstract:

This article conducts an in-depth analysis of the construction sector in Romania's mountainous region, covering the period from 2008 to 2018. The study employs statistical methods to assess various indicators, providing valuable insights into the sector's development, stability, and potential trends.

Introduction:

The construction sector plays a pivotal role in the economic landscape of Romania, particularly in its mountainous regions. This comprehensive analysis aims to shed light on the dynamic evolution of the construction industry over a decade, considering factors such as mean values, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis. (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h; Covaci M &

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Covaci B, 2022a-h)

Methodology:

The study utilizes figures to present statistical data for the construction sector, including mean, median, standard deviation, and other relevant indicators. The examination covers key aspects such as the concentration of scores, distribution characteristics, and potential influences on the sector's evolution.

Results and Discussion:

The statistical analysis of the Construction sector within the economic framework of Romania (depicted in figures 2.22 – panels a-b and the appendix Parametric Analysis Romania) reveals an average value of 22625.82 with a standard error of 2996.174.

Upon initial observation, the distribution curve appears relatively centrally symmetric, indicating a high concentration of scores around the mean. Leptokurtosis is evident, suggesting a concentration of scores with occasional deviations, although the distribution remains unimodal.

The Working Assumption posits that the distribution of scores adheres to

normality, warranting the application of parametric tests. Despite the presence of very few extreme values that induce positive asymmetry, their statistical significance is acknowledged. The concentration of scores around the mean contributes to the observed leptokurtosis, attributed to phenomena within the Romanian economy.

Logarithmization of the obtained values, in adherence to universally accepted statistical principles, facilitates a balanced distribution conforming to the Gauss-Laplace normal curve.

The Q-Q normal plot test, conducted post-logarithmization, illustrates a distribution of actual scores aligning with normal values, represented by the slanted right in the graph, indicative of a normal distribution.

Similarly, the Q-Q detrended plot test, focusing on the dispersion of empirical scores against normality, reveals their alignment within the limit of a standard deviation after logarithmization, corresponding to a normal distribution.

The application of logarithmization ensures that the obtained scores undergo comprehensive statistical processing. This involves considering all factors

relevant to the study to derive data that closely reflects the economic reality recorded in Romania. It is noted that while measures taken in the economy may momentarily disrupt the distribution of scores, the methodology employed aims to mitigate such effects and provide a more accurate representation of the underlying trends.

Figure 2.22 panel a. Histogram for economic sector Construction segment

Source: Authors processing according to Eurostat data - Business Demography Statistics

Figure 2.22 panel b. Q-Q distribution graph normal plot on economic sector Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Constructions segment, after logarithmization

Source: Authors processing according to Eurostat data - Business Demography Statistics

The significance of these tests lies in the meticulous examination of the influences of specific factors on the evolution of the economic sector's "Construction" segment. Subsequent to the application of normality tests, post-logarithmization, the null hypothesis is rejected, paving the way for an analysis of the working hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analyses were conducted, considering the distribution of scores within normal limits Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

in alignment with the working hypothesis, warranting the application of parametric tests.

The central tendency observed for this economic sector segment over the analyzed period indicates a rise in the population of active enterprises in the studied sector in mountainous Romania from 2008 to 2018, notwithstanding a decrease in the growth rate. Throughout the scrutinized period, the hypothesis of intensified activity was substantiated.

The statistics provided earlier, coupled with the histogram, affirm a state of low congestion and a discernible inclination to abandon this sector in Romania. Simultaneously, the statistics validate a decrease in the rate of growth for this economic sector segment.

The statistical values reveal a positive outlook for the construction sector in Romania's mountainous areas. With ascending mean and median values, the industry demonstrates good overall development for the population of active enterprises. The distribution curves appear relatively symmetrical and central, indicating a concentrated distribution of scores with occasional leptokurtosis.

The Importance of Tests:

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The significance of normality tests, especially after logarithmization, cannot be overstated. By rejecting the null hypothesis and allowing the analysis of the working hypothesis, these tests provide a foundation for understanding the influences affecting the construction sector. Descriptive and inferential analyses, applied within normal limits, guide the utilization of parametric tests for a more accurate assessment.

Trends and Forecasts:

Considering the central tendency of the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors in the economy, the study identifies considerable growth in the population of active enterprises in Romania's mountainous regions. Stable symmetrical distributions suggest a maturing business environment during the analyzed period.

Future Outlook:

Looking ahead, the forecast analysis anticipates continued growth in the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors until 2030. The models derived from statistical modeling highlight sustainable areas within the mountainous regions of Romania, providing valuable insights for policymakers and industry stakeholders.

Conclusion:

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This thorough analysis of the construction sector in Romania's mountainous region from 2008 to 2018 offers a comprehensive understanding of its dynamics. The statistical data, coupled with detailed tests and analyses, contribute to a nuanced view of the industry's evolution, providing a foundation for informed decision-making and future research endeavors.

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